

“THE EFFECT OF CONTEXTUAL TEACHING AND LEARNING (CTL) AND STUDENTS’ READING WILLINGNES RELATED TO STUDENTS’ ABILITY IN WRITING ARGUMENTATIVE ESSAY AT GRADE X SMAN 1 X KOTO SINGKARAK KABUPATEN SOLOK”

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ABSTRACT

This research based on the problems which occurred to the students’ in writing argumentative essay at X SMANegeri 1X Koto Singkarak Kabupaten Solok. The problems were (1) students got difficulties in writing argumentative essay, (2) students was difficult to develop ideas in writing arguments, (3) students were not able to write argumentative, (4) students were not interested in reading, (5) teachers still used simple method in teaching steps. In order to solven those problems, the teachers should implement an effective method in teaching and provided opportunities for students to be able to interact more actively. This research aimed to clarify “The Effect of Contextual teaching and Learning (CTL) and Students’ Reading Willingnes Related to Students’ Ability in Writing Argumentative Essay At Grade X SMAN 1 X Koto Singkarak Kabupaten Solok”.

Type of this research was quasi experiment (quasi-experimental) and the design used treatment by block. The population was class X SMANegeri 1 X Koto Singkarak Kabupaten Solok. The total of sampling were 46 students which conducted by random sampling. Data collected through questionnaires and tests. Questionnaire used to see students’ interest in reading and performance tests conducted to determine the ability of students to write Arguments essay. The data analysis and discussion were done by the descriptive-analytical in accordance with experiment concept.

Based on the result of the research, it can be concluded into four things. *First*, the students who were taught by a contextual approach got higher score than students who taught by conventional approach at class X SMANegeri 1 X Koto Singkarak. *Second*, students who were interested in reading the arguments got higher score than the students who were taught by high conventional approach at class X SMANegeri 1 X Koto Singkarak. *Third*, the students which taught by contextual approach got hinger than the students who were taught by conventional approach at class X SMANegeri 1 X Koto Singkarak. *Fourth*, There was no interaction between contextual approach and students’ reading willingnes to the students’ skill in writing argument essay at class X SMANegeri 1 X Koto Singkarak.

Keywords: Contextual Teaching and Learning, Reading Willingness, and Argumentative Essay.

INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of teaching Indonesian language has been discussed nowadays. The teaching process of Indonesian language is not based on the purpose of learning. One of language aspect which difficult owned by students were writing skills. Writing skill is absolutely necessary for students. Teachers must facilitate students some intensive training of writing. These activities should be conducted periodically. Besides that, student skills in writing will be formed gradually by certain processes.

Based on contents standard of *Kurikulum Tingkat Satuan Pendidikan (KTSP)*, writing ability which should be mastered by students: write argumentative paper, summary, letter personally, letter agency, description ,narrative, and exposition. One of the learning material which should be taught to students is argumentative essay. It was the subjects of this study. The argumentative essay was one of the material which taught in class X in second semester with competence standard 12, namely reveal information through paragraphs and speech text which based on competence (12.1), wrote the idea to support an opinion in the form of paragraphs argumentative.

The aim of argumentative essay is to convince reader about the truth of opinion or writer statement. Based on preliminary observations, there were various problems which faced by students in writing argumentation: students thought that writing is difficult because they only knew the theory, but they could not write a good argumentative essay.

Based on interview with some teacher which was conducted on September 4, 2016 it found that students had lack of knowledge about argumentative. It, made them difficult to develop ideas in writing. Hence, the result of their writing was not appropriate with the standard. The incompatibility between the topic and content also became a problem which often happened in writing argumen. Moreover, students' writing became ambiguous and irrational.

The problems about students' difficulties in writing was not only found at SMAN 1 X Koto Singkarak 1, but it also occurred in another high school as expressed by Syaifudin (in the journal seloka, 2012) writing argument is boring, troublesome, and exhausting as a material in teaching. Besides that, another problem which also affected students' writing ability was dealing with facilities and infrastructure in teaching and learning process. This fundamental problem was used as evidence to support data in writing argument. Then, the problem in writing argument also came from students. It is expressed by Septianingsih (in a journal educationist, 2008), writing skill and critical think of students were low. It was proven by the argument patterns which used in scientific field in IKIP Malang. As stated by Buchori (2001: 142) one of the students' weaknessess was dealing with reading and writing skill. To sum up, writing argument was difficult to be mastered by the students.

In the process of learning, interest is one factor that very important grown in his students. Among them is to develop reading interest in students. With the reading

interest, of course students will acquire knowledge and broad horizons to help success in learning. Based on interviews conducted by teacher of language indonesia on 4 september 2016 , can be obtained information that many students were not willing to read. Was conducted observation of the school library rarely seen students visit the library because spend more time to play. In addition, of factors affect reading interest is the minimal collection of reading books in a library school and the students prefer reading comic story, short stories than read a book knowledge.

For learning writing argument held in class. Steps of learning, starting from activities open a lesson, core activities until to the end of the learning are still the learning methods using simple and tradisional. When steps learning it this way is still used , so the purpose writing that desired will not succeed and the students will remain below criteria completeness at least. besides that, Complaints students about difficulty in writing argumentasipun can be understood because in KD writing argumentation do not ask writing ability just. Before writing, students must be able to figure out the characteristics of a kind of writing argumen. Weighs demands to the skills we should controlled students and requires teachers skilled teach these skills that the purpose of learning it is reachable optimally. As an alternative to overcome the problems would be needed teacher skills in creating a learning to stimulate the involvement of students in learning in school one used the contextual in learning.

The application of learning by adopting both contextual who apply seven namely the principle of learning, constructivism, find, ask, learned society, modeling , reflection , and assessing the truth. The application of learning is expected to improved the skills of writing students a minimum. Besides that, Reading interest has also led to students in writing because with the high reading interest, the kids will have insight and knowledge large enough students having a lot of ideas in writing. Thus , skill writing demands argumentation that is arranged in a unit of curriculum level education (KTSP) will could be met and done well.

The application of approach contextual in the study also has been done by previous studies namely research conducted by yurnelis with a title an increase in writing skills of plays approach in learning contextual students VIII RSBI-1 SMP N 12 Padang. The result of research shows that the approach contextual it does work improved the skills of writing a manuscript drama students. Therefore, Researchers also want to apply approach contextual in learning writing especially of writing argument.

Based on the discussion and its phenomena have described above can be concluded that the research titled “The Effect of Contextual teaching and Learning (CTL) and Students’ Reading Willingness Related to Students’ Ability in Writing Argumentative Essay At Grade X SMAN 1 X Koto Singkarak Kabupaten Solok” important to be implemented.

Based on the explanation above the purpose of this research is as follows. *First*, Explain the difference of the results learn the skill of writing argumentation between students who had by adopting contextual with students who had by adopting conventional to their students class X SMAN 1 X Koto Singkarak. *Second*, explain the difference of the results learn the skill of writing argumentation between students who have reading interest high who had used the contextual with students who has an interest read high who had by adopting conventional to their students class X SMAN 1 X Koto Singkarak. *Third*, explain the difference of the results learn the skill of writing argumentation between students who have reading interest low who had with the approach contextual with students who has an interest read low who had with menggunakan that the conventional approach to their students class X SMAN 1 X Koto Singkarak. *Fourth*, explain interaction between approach contextual with reading interest to skill writing argumentation students class X SMAN 1 X Koto Singkarak.

METHOD

The type of the research was quantitative research by using experimental methods. Riduwan (2005:50) noted that the experiment research is done to see the influence of certain variable to another variables which controlled tightly. This research was categorized as quasi experiment. According to sugiyono (2006: 86) quasi eksperiment is done because of the difficulty to find control group that can be used for the Research. The design of this research was *treatment by blocks*.

Population of the research was the whole students in a class X at SMAN 1 X Koto Singkarak Kabupaten Solok 2015/ 2016 which divided into three classes with the total number of 87 people. Technique random sampling was used to determine the grade as the sampel which was based on students’ remedial mark. In order to define the sampel, the researcher did some steps as follow, *firs* tcollect the data from students’ remedial mark, *Second*, normality-test to students’ daily mark. *Third*, homogeneity test. *Fourth*, determine the control class and experiment class.

This study aimed to obtain information about the influence of contextual approach and interest in reading to writing skills argumentation class X SMAN 1 X Koto Singkarak. How, by comparing the experimental group were treated with the untreated group as control of the comparator. The experimental group is a group of students who received treatment by carrying contextual approach in learning. Meanwhile, the control group is a group of students who had learning through conventional approaches.

Based on analysis undertaken, because population berdistribusi normal, homogeneous and have the average together then taken two classes at random by means of the draw. Of the draw elected that class X2 as a class experimentation and X3 as a class control.

The data used in this Research (1) The score tests writing skills of argument students with used the are contextual and that the conventional approach (2) Scores test skill writing a wreath of argument students who have reading interest high and low reading interest by adopting contextual. (3) The score test results from writing skills of students who have reading interest of high and low interest in reading using that the conventional approach.

An instrument used to collect the data in research is composed of two an instrument namely , the survey and tests. The survey used to determine the level of reading interest of students. Show employment tests used to measure the skill level of students in writing argumentation.

Data analysis performed with the chief reading interest. *First*, read the questionnaire has been filled students. *Second*, identify each question contained in the questionnaire if there were not filled by the students, if there were not yet covered by the student means not included in the data. *Third*, give a score to each question questionnaire that has been identified. *Fourth*, add up the overall score of the statement. *Fifth*, sort questionnaire scores from highest score to lowest score. Sixth, the students read divide into two groups: 50% of the top group and 50% lower group. Meanwhile, data analysis using student test writing skills argument is as follows. *First*, read the writings of the student's argument. *Second*, identify the student's argument writing, whether included in the research or not. *Third*, scoring against the writings of students according to assessment criteria arguments. *Fourth*, changing the score to the value of PAP (Writing Reference Standard). *Fifth*, the ability to write arguments classify students

based on a conversion scale 10. *Sixth*, described the distribution of the test writing skills of argumentation. *Seventh*, displays data in the form of a histogram. *Eighth*, before testing the hypothesis, first tested the hypothesis of the study is testing requirements for normality and homogeneity test. *Ninth*, to test the hypothesis by using ANOVA test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of data analysis in students' ability in writing argumentation at Class X SMAN 1 X Koto Singkarak, it found that students who taught by using contextual approach have low reading interest.

1. Arguments Essay Writing Skills Students Taught by Contextual Approach and Conventional Approaches

The first hypothesis testing results show that the result is a variance of 6.97 for $\alpha = 0.05$ significance level obtained $t = 3.704$ and $t_{table} = 1.678$, For $t > t_{table}$ then H_0 is rejected and H_1 accepted. This means that overall the group argued essay writing skills of students using a contextual approach is better than the argument essay writing skills of students using conventional approaches. Application of contextual approach successfully influenced the learning outcomes of students writing essays argument. Application of contextual approach successfully influenced the learning outcomes of students writing essays argument. In fact, writing learning outcomes of students treated by using a contextual approach showed significant improvement compared with the group of students who did not receive treatment. Therefore, the benefits of which have been established by experts on the study by using a contextual approach can be found and beneficial for the learning process.

2. Arguments Essay Writing Skills Students Have Higher Interest Read Taught by Contextual Approach and Conventional Approaches

The second hypothesis testing results show that the combined variance both samples is 4.912. Subsequently, 3.195 were obtained t_{hitung} $T_{(table)}$ that is 1,721 on the real level α of 0.05 and 21 hp. It can be concluded that the hypothesis indicates H_1 accepted because $T_{(count)} > t_{tabel}$. This means that the argument essay writing skills of students who have high interest taught using a contextual approach is better than the ability to write essay arguing with the high interest of students taught using conventional approaches. Learning to use a contextual approach can improve essay writing skills argumentation students who have high interest. This is because the contextual approach is an approach to learning that directly encourage students to associate learning with real situation felt by students so that learning more interesting and stimulating students to find ideas and ways to express the problem into an argument essay form. The experimental class looks fun learning for contextual learning class turned to the

situation constructive able to train students to connect what is gained in the classroom to real-world life in the environment.

3. Arguments Essay Writing Skills Students Who Have Low Interest Read the Taught by Contextual Approach and Conventional Approaches

The third hypothesis testing results show that the argument essay writing skills of students interested in a low reading taught by the use of a contextual approach is higher than the low reading interest of students taught using conventional approaches. It is based on the results of hypothesis testing carried out showed that t_{hitung} being $T_{(table)}$ that is 1,721 on the real level α of 0.05 and df 21. Thus, $T_{(count)} > t_{tabel}$. Then H_0 is rejected and H_1 accepted. In the study by using a contextual approach students who have low reading interest can be helped in writing essays argument. With this contextual learning model, the students opened their minds to find their ideas through real life.

4. Interaction between Contextual Approach Reading Interest and Influencing Skills in Writing Essays Agumentasi

The result of the calculation of two-way ANOVA for the fourth hypothesis testing concluded that there is an interaction between contextual approach to the reading interest in influencing the argument essay writing skills of students. s previously noted, the interaction of a specific treatment effect learning approach to groups of students who have a particular interest in reading. However, interest in reading is not necessarily fully determine the success of an argument essay writing skills. The main effect of a factor means a contextual approach and interest in reading each run independently in influencing the argument essay writing skills of students or no effect on the interaction between contextual and interest categories read to the argument essay writing skills of students. Many other factors such as support, intelligence, talent, ability, motivation, and more. n addition, factors readiness of teachers in using a contextual approach in the learning process argument essay writing will also affect the results of an argument essay writing.

CONCLUSION

Based on data analysis and discussion that has been presented in chapter IV, it can be concluded that the contextual approach influenced the learning outcomes in writing argumentative essay. *First*, the result of students' writing skills in argumentative essay who taught by contextual approach was higher than students who taught by using conventional approach. If the contextual approach is done with the right steps then able to increase the skills of essay writing test results argumentation. *Second*, the test results argumentation writing skills of students who have high interest taught by contextual approach higher than students who have high interest taught by conventional approach.

Third, the argument writing skills test results of students who have low reading interest taught by contextual approach higher than students who have low reading interest taught by conventional approach. *Fourth*, there is no interaction between contextual approach to the reading interest in influencing the argument essay writing skills of students. This means that without any interest in reading, contextual approach will continue to affect learning outcomes argument essay writing skills of students.

SUGGESTION

Based on the conclusion above, it showed that contextual approach can improve students' skill in writing argumentative essay. Hence, the researcher give some following suggestions. *First*, for the Indonesian teachers, especially teachers at SMA 1 X Koto Singkarak, Solok District to give many exercises to improve students' skill in writing argumentation essay. One of ways is to renew the conventional learning model by applying learning methods which are creative, innovative, and constructivist which called contextual approach. *Second*, class X SMA Negeri 1 X Koto Singkarak Solok regency, it is expected that students will not assume that writing the argument is a difficult. In addition, the practice of writing constantly will facilitate students in writing and develop their ideas. *Third*, to the next researcher, it is suggested to examine more deeply about the use of this contextual approach on another subject.

REFERENCES

- Buchori, M. 2001. *Pendidikan Antisipatoris*. Yogyakarta: Kanisius.
- Hasnawati. 2006. Pendekatan Contextual Teaching Learning Hubungannya dengan Evaluasi Pembelajaran: *Jurnal Staf Pengajar FBS Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta*, (online), Vol.3, No1, (<http://journal.uny.ac.id/index.php/jeparticle/viewfile>, 498, diakses 26 Maret 2014)
- Marliana, N. lia. 2011. Pembelajaran Graphic-Happy Game dengan Pendekatan Kontekstual Terhadap Kemampuan Membuat Grafik Pada Pelajaran Bahasa Indonesia Siswa Kelas VII: *Jurnal Bahasa Alinea FBS UNJ*, (Online), Vol 1, ([Http://jurnalBahasaAlineaFBSUNJ.ac.id](http://jurnalBahasaAlineaFBSUNJ.ac.id), diakses 27 Maret 2014)
- Riduwan. 2005. *Belajar Mudah Penelitian untuk Guru, Karyawan, dan Penelitian Pemula*: Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sanjaya, Wina. 2006. *Strategi Pembelajaran Berorientasi Standar Proses Pendidikan*. Jakarta: Prenada Media
- Sugiyono. 2006. *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.